

concentration of the rice plant with time may be explained by the plant's physiology during this period. In the first 4 days after transplanting, the roots were inactive. That might have limited the plant's water and nutrient absorption as reflected in the plants' withering, and yellowing, and their reduced nitrogen content. After 4 days, plant roots recovered from transplanting shock and regulated the water and nutrient supply. That condition was indicated by a return of greenness and increased nitrogen content in the plants. After 6 days, nitrogen was appropriated in the synthesis of metabolites and for fast plant growth. During this time the nitrogen supply probably was not commensurate with the rapid plant growth; thus the nitrogen content of the plants decreased sharply because of the "dilution effect."

To increase the efficiency of fertilizer use, it may be beneficial to apply nitrogen 5 days after transplanting. This

Effect of fungicide seed treatment on rice seedling growth

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The seedborne nature of sheath blight disease of rice caused by *Rhizoctonia solani* Kuhn has been established. Seeds of ADT3 1 were collected from sheath blight-affected fields, treated with test fungicides, and stored in polythene bags for 3 days. The test fungicides thiophanate, captafol, fenaminosulf, triarimol, PCNB, carbendazim, captan, chloroneb, carboxin, benomyl, triphenyltin acetate, Agrosan, thiram, oxycarboxin, MEMC, chlorothalonil were used at 0.05, 0.1, and 0.2% levels. The treated seeds were tested for germination, seedling growth, and vigor. Some treated seeds were stored for 8 months and then tested for viability.

Benomyl, chlorothalonil, and carboxin increased seed germination considerably over the control. Oxycarboxin, carboxin, chlorothalonil, and benomyl significantly increased shoot growth. Carbendazim,

Comparison of basal and delayed application of first dose of nitrogen on two rice cultivars. Ludhiana, India.

Treatment ^a	Yield (t/ha)	
	Palman 579	PR106
T ₁	5.4	6.4
T ₂	5.7	6.6

^a T₁ = 40 kg N/ha at transplanting + 40 kg N 3 wk after transplanting (WT) + 40 kg N 6 WT. T₂ = 40 kg N/ha at 7 days after transplanting + 40 kg N 3 WT + 40 kg N 6 WT.

observation is supported by results of a replicated field experiment conducted on Fatehpur loamy sand in the 1978 kharif (Jul-Oct) (see table).

The data show that application of nitrogen at 7 days after transplanting gave 0.3 t/ha more yield than its application at transplanting. Therefore, fertilizer use efficiency may be higher if the first dose of nitrogen is applied 5–7 days after transplanting. But further large-scale field testing in different environments is needed. ■

triarimol, captafol, thiram, oxycarboxin, chlorothalonil, benomyl, and captan at 0.2%) increased the root growth of rice seedlings. Seedlings from the treated seeds were more vigorous than the control. Seeds treated with oxycarboxin and MEMC maintained more than 90% seed viability after 8 months of storage. ■

Azolla manuring for rice

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In earlier trials Srinivasan and Pari showed that azolla incorporation 1 week before planting at 10, 20, and 30 t/ha (nitrogen levels as high as 100 kg/ha) gave yields equal to 25, 50, and 75 kg N/ha, respectively. They also found that growing azolla until harvest but without incorporation gave no beneficial effects.

Because the field cannot be kept fallow for growing azolla after the kuruvai harvest, it was decided to grow azolla among the planted crop and incorporate it after it covered the surface. Three replicated trials were laid out

during 1978 thaladi with inoculum levels of 1, 2, and 3 t/ha at nitrogen levels of 0 to 100 kg/ha in slabs of 25 kg. P₂O₅ and K₂O were uniformly applied at 50 kg/ha before planting. The test variety was IR20. Azolla was sown 1 week after planting; the water level was maintained at 5 cm. The inoculum levels at 1, 2, and 3 t/ha covered the field 55, 33, and 15 days after application, respectively. Azolla was incorporated after the water was drained.

In the trial where azolla inoculum was applied at 3 t/ha, a yield increase equal

Effect of azolla manuring on grain yield of rice. Aduthurai, India.

N levels (kg/ha)	Yield (t/ha) at azolla inoculum level of		
	1 t/ha	2 t/ha	3 t/ha
0	2.9	2.8	2.9
0 + azolla	3.0	3.1	3.4
25	3.5	3.3	3.2
25 + azolla	3.5	3.5	3.6
50	3.6	3.5	3.1
50 + azolla	3.8	3.8	4.0
75	4.0	3.9	4.2
75 + azolla	4.1	4.0	4.6
100	4.4	4.3	4.7
100 + azolla	4.4	4.5	5.2
CD (P = 0.05%)	0.4	0.5	0.3

to that of 25 kg N/ha was observed (see table). In trials with inoculum levels of 1 and 2 t/ha there was no appreciable yield increase because of the delayed incorporation of azolla (62 and 40 days after planting, respectively). ■

Soil loss due to roguing in rice seed production plots

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The roguing of offtypes is a standard practice in pure seed production programs. The major roguing operation takes place after flowering. Uprooting the entire plant speeds the removal of rogues, but a considerable amount of topsoil sticking to the roots is also removed from the plot in the process.

We randomly sampled rogues uprooted from our rice seed-production plots,

collected them on the roadside, carefully removed the soil sticking to the roots, and later air-dried it. The soil was a red sandy loam. On weighing the air-dried soil, we noted that an average of 0.7 kg

of dry soil was removed for each hill uprooted.

At a 20- × 10-cm spacing the plant population in our plots is 500,000 hills/ha. If a modest 10% of the hills are removed

as rogues, the estimated soil losses would be 35 t/ha in a single crop season. To avoid this staggering loss of topsoil, we suggest that plants be rogued by cutting them close to the base. ■

Introduction of puddling, an Asian technique, in rice production in Colombia

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Rice production in Colombia is characterized by high yields and high production costs. In the same period

that yields increased by 77% (the national average for irrigated rice is 5.5 t/ha), production costs increased by 670%, (up to about US\$1,200/ha). Those trends make further yield increases difficult.

Therefore the National Rice Growers Federation (FEDEARROZ) is investigating the introduction of puddling techniques from Asia into Colombian

rice fields. In 1979 an intensive program, conducted to provide technical assistance to farmers, included help with plot design, mechanization, and crop management. About 5,000 ha are now puddled.

Puddling has increased the average yield in that area by about 7% and lowered production costs by about 20%. ■

Rice-based cropping systems

Traditional cultural practices in rainfed wetland rice cultivation in Moyna Basin, Midnapore, West Bengal, India

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Little is known about traditional cultivation practices for the traditional tall indicas cultivated in deepwater areas. In the 1977 wet season the problems and behavior of the varieties were surveyed in the 4,000-ha Moyna Bheel basin area in Midnapore District, West Bengal. A water regime of about 1.5–2 m is usually reached in about 50% of the basin area during the peak precipitation period; the water remains stagnant for 3–4 months. The average annual precipitation is about 1,800 mm, most of which falls from June to October. Two factors govern successful rice cultivation in such lands; proper land preparation at sowing, and proper stand establishment before inundation of the rice plants.

The land in the basin area can be classified into three main water depth categories: 1.0 m, 1–1.5 m, and more than 1.5 m.

The soil in the 1.0-m depth category remains moist until March. After harvest, the stubble (91–122 cm long) is left to

dry. The dry stubble is burned to destroy hibernating insects and wild rice seeds, and to facilitate tillage in the black peat soil. The presoaked seeds are then sown at 125 kg/ha and the land is plowed once and then laddered. Pregerminated seeds are then sown again at the same rate; the land is plowed again and laddered 10–12 times to level and compact the soil. Depending on soil condition, the field is further laddered until the topsoil consists of fine particles.

Land in the 1- to 1.5-m category is plowed twice and then kept fallow for 10–15 days. If there is no rain, dry seeds are sown in dry soil. The field is laddered after the rains come and germination begins. If soil moisture conditions permit, laddering is done three or four times.

Where water depth exceeds 1.5 m, dry seeds are generally sown after the harvest of the dry season crop; the land is then alternatively plowed and laddered. Dry or germinated seeds are generally broadcast, depending on the soil moisture content.

For fertilizer, Moyna Basin farmers apply bonemeal at 125 kg/ha, and decomposed farmyard manure and ash at 2.5 t/ha immediately after sowing. Progressive basin area farmers report that a rainless period of 1–1.5 months is

desirable for proper soil condition and minimum weed growth. Weeding is generally practiced when water accumulates 1.5–2 months after sowing.

A good stand is usually established about 2 months after sowing, before much water has accumulated. When the crop has attained a good stand, the plants can withstand submergence and waterlogging. Average yields of 3 t/ha are common.

The following traditional varieties are predominant in the basin:

For areas where water depth is about 1.0 m: Amol, Kamod, Gaira, Bhuto, Bakui.

For areas where water reaches 1.5 m and deeper: Pankalas green, Pankalas pigmented, Tangra, Bauskata.

In the basin where water reaches 1.5 m or deeper, rice plants were uprooted and their tillering patterns and nodal rooting were studied. Tillering was from the base only and nodal roots were present. The traditional varieties can yield about 3 t/ha, provided fields are inundated about 2 months after sowing. In the past, when water in such areas had currents, varieties with nodal tillers were grown. But since channels and bunds for flood prevention had been installed, farmers have preferred basal tillering rices that yield better and are harvested more easily. ■